

IEA Wind Task 52 LAC Summer Games 2024

30s Sprint

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Abstract: This work presents a solution for the IEA Wind Task 52 LAC Summer Games, specifically targeting the “30s Sprint” discipline. The objective is to enhance the response of a Lidar-assisted control system for wind turbines when subjected to a 12 m/s extreme operational gust (EOG). The proposed approach integrates a multivariable feedforward control strategy with a neural network-based pitch angle prediction. The controller modifies a conventional feedforward pitch system to maintain constant generator torque by using LIDAR to anticipate wind speed variations. The neural network is trained to predict the required pitch angle based on the Tip Speed Ratio (TSR) and thrust coefficient to reduce the fore-aft moment. Simulations using the OpenFAST aeroelastic model demonstrate significant improvements over baseline controllers, achieving a 67.9 % reduction in rotor speed deviation and a 90 % reduction in tower base fore-aft bending moment deviation. Additionally, the controller reduces rotor thrust by 22.4% compared to traditional feedback systems. These results indicate that the proposed multivariable feedforward controller, complemented by a deep neural network, provides a robust solution for improving wind turbine performance under extreme wind conditions.

1 Introduction

The present work aims at addressing the IEA Wind Task 52 Summer Games, based on Lidar-Assisted-Control, as a final work for the masters course: “Controller Design for Wind Turbines and Wind Farms”.

The task consists on proposing a solution to the second discipline “30s Sprint”. In this discipline, the goal is improve a wind turbine’s Lidar-assisted controller’s response, when subjected to a 12 m/s extreme operational gust (EOG). The main objective is to adequate the controller’s response using LIDAR as a technology to obtain a preview of the rotor effective wind speed (REWS). A correct response would smooth or even cancel out the effect of the EOG in the turbine and therefore prevent rapid the changes in the rotor speed and tower motion [2].

To evaluate the performance of the controller, the cost function is introduced, with the objective of minimizing it.

$$Cost = \frac{\max(|\Omega - \Omega_0|)}{\Omega_0} + \frac{\max(|M_{yT} - M_{yT0}|)}{M_{yT0}} \quad (1)$$

In this context, Ω represents the rotor speed, with Ω_0 denoting its steady-state value. Similarly, M_{yT} refers to the fore-aft bending moment at the tower base, while

M_{yT0} corresponds to its steady-state value.

The original controller is implemented in Matlab/Simulink and it corresponds to a simplified version of the ROSCO controller with a feedforward collective pitch controller, particularly focused on the power production in region 3 [1]. The Simulink blocks can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Simulink model of the ROSCO controller including a simple feedforward controller.

As the figure portrays, the controller consists of a pitch + torque controller with the addition of a feedforward collective pitch controller (CPC), which takes on the LIDAR signal of the rotor effective wind speed (REWS). The input to the pitch controller is the filtered generator speed, which enters a PI controller. The torque controller maintains constant torque throughout the operation (rated torque).

The feedforward collective pitch controller takes on the real-time measurement of the REWS, which then enters a steady-state pitch angle vs speed lookup table. The signal is derived and delayed a certain buffer time T_{buffer} , and then proceeds to the CPC.

The alternative proposed in this work modifies the existing controller by introducing structural changes. The main idea is to adapt the feedforward pitch controller to compensate for the effect of REWS on aerodynamic thrust, while maintaining constant generator torque. This is achieved by using the feedforward pitch action as an input to a feedforward torque generator block. This approach is a modification of the Multivariable Extension based on Simplified Calculations (MESCAL) proposed by [4] and utilizes OpenFAST simulations to evaluate the response of the wind turbine model.

The structure used for this article is presented next. Section 2 provides a background with the knowledge and previous work in which this article is based. Section 3 gives a walkthrough of the methodology used to achieve the main objective and its implications. Section 4 shows the results obtained and its analysis and Section 5 presents the conclusions.

2 Background

Lidar-assisted control has emerged as a promising approach for enhancing wind turbine performance by reducing structural loads and increasing energy output. Unlike conventional controllers, which typically respond to wind changes with delays due to rotor inertia, LIDAR systems can measure wind speeds and estimate the effective rotor speed at hub height in advance, enabling more proactive control strategies. A key advantage of this approach is the ability to integrate the feedforward signal into existing feedback controllers with minimal modifications. This integration allows for the prediction of future control actions to compensate for anticipated variations, such as those encountered in Region 3, using analytical models combined with LIDAR measurements.

Specifically, Collective Pitch Feedforward Control (CPFC) has demonstrated significant effectiveness in mitigating structural loads during high wind conditions and has been successfully integrated with traditional feedback controllers in various practical applications [6]. For instance, [5] introduced a feedforward pitch controller that utilizes LIDAR measurements alongside a static pitch curve to generate a feedforward signal, compensating for fluctuations in wind speed. A block diagram of the controller is illustrated in Figure 2.

In addition to pitch control, feedforward torque control has been extensively studied for its ability to reduce rotor speed variations and stabilize generator power. [7] proposed a nonlinear feedforward torque control strategy

Figure 2: Collective pitch feedforward controller. Adapted from [6].

and a linear disturbance accommodating control (DAC) to enhance a baseline PI feedback controller. This approach aims to attenuate wind disturbances affecting rotor speed regulation and reduce structural loads, particularly in operations below rated wind speeds. Similarly, [3] developed a simulation model for power regulation in horizontal-axis wind turbines using pitch control and feedforward strategies. Their model, which integrates PID control for both pitch angle and generator torque, demonstrated that feedforward control improves dynamic response and reduces rotor speed variations, especially when wind speeds exceed rated values.

Moreover, [6] investigated the integration of LIDAR technology with a flatness-based feedforward control strategy, termed Tower Equilibrium Accommodation (TEQUILA). This method, applied during the transition between partial and full load operations, aims to minimize structural loads and regulate rotor speed by utilizing real-time wind speed data from LIDAR. The control strategy, based on a simplified nonlinear wind turbine model (SLOW), optimizes the prediction and planning of rotor speed and tower motion while maintaining computational efficiency. The TEQUILA controller includes a trajectory planning module, generating smooth control inputs for collective pitch control (CPC) and indirect speed control (ISC), while considering actuator constraints, leading to load reductions in simulations.

Building on this, [4] proposed a simplified version of their multivariable feedforward controller, which calculates desired control actions using rotor-effective wind speed (REWS) preview data and a linearized model for torque and pitch control. This version reduces computational complexity while maintaining performance, achieving load reductions and consistent rotor and tower motion during turbulent wind conditions, though it exhibited a slight decrease in power production.

Overall, feedforward control strategies, particularly when integrated with LIDAR measurements, have shown considerable potential for improving wind turbine performance by reducing structural loads and enhancing control responsiveness. This background establishes a robust foundation for the methodology of this work, which fo-

cuses on implementing and testing a feedforward Collective Pitch Control Strategy and a feedforward generator torque control using LIDAR signals to optimize wind turbine control systems.

3 Methodology

In this work, the Multivariable Extension based on Simplified Calculations (MESCAL) method proposed by [4] is employed to design a multivariable feedforward controller for wind turbines. The methodology is structured as follows:

1. **Control Action Calculation:** The inverse model of wind turbine operational data is used to compute the desired generator torque (M_{gen}) and pitch angle (θ_{ff}) feedforward action. These control actions are designed to mitigate the effects of tower fore-aft bending and maintain a constant generator torque in region 3 of operation.
2. **Machine Learning-based Pitch Angle Prediction:** The pitch angle is predicted using a fully connected neural network, which takes as input the current Tip Speed Ratio (denote as λ) and the Thrust Coefficient. The thrust coefficient C_t is calculated based on a desired constant thrust, as defined by equation (?). The neural network is trained using steady-state data around a specific set of possible operating points. To maintain constant torque during pitch feedback variations, the generator torque is adjusted by adding or subtracting a corrective term (ΔM_g).
3. **Integration with Feedback Control:** The feedforward control actions are integrated with a conventional feedback controller. Specifically, the feedforward pitch rate is updated and incorporated into the feedback controller, while the generator torque is adjusted by updating the torque deviation required to maintain constant torque. This combined approach ensures that the system responds effectively to wind speed variations in region 3 of operation.

This simplified methodology retains several key advantages of the flatness-based approach, including reduced rotor speed variation and improved tower motion stability. Additionally, the integration of a trained deep neural network allows for seamless incorporation of real operational data into the control logic through predictive functions, enhancing both system adaptability and overall performance.

The control variables are fed into the 15 MW NREL wind turbine model, which is simulated using OpenFAST—a physics-based engineering tool designed to simulate the coupled dynamic response of wind turbines.

OpenFAST integrates aerodynamic, hydrodynamic (for offshore structures), control system (servo), electrical, and structural (elastic) dynamics models to enable fully coupled nonlinear aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulations in the time domain. The output of each time step simulation are inputs of the feedback control.

3.1 Control Scheme

Figure 3: Control block diagram.

The control system block diagram is illustrated in Figure 3. The feedforward pitch controller, shown in Figure 4, requires three key inputs: the LIDAR-estimated rotor-effective wind speed (REWS), the generator speed, and the steady-state thrust. Based on these inputs, the controller calculates the tip-speed ratio (λ) and the thrust coefficient (C_t). These values are processed through a neural network, which predicts the required pitch angle, θ_{ff} . This pitch angle is designed to maintain constant thrust and, consequently, stabilize tower motion.

Figure 4: Feedforward pitch control block diagram.

The C_t value is obtained using Equation 2, where F_a is the steady-state aerodynamic thrust, ρ is the air density, R is the rotor radius and V_{OL} is the LIDAR estimated REWS.

$$C_t = \frac{F_{a_{ss}}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho\pi R^2 V_{OL}^2} \quad (2)$$

The predicted pitch angle, θ_{ff} , is differentiated to generate a feedforward pitch rate signal. This signal is then amplified by a proportional gain K , which is optimized using brute force optimization, and incorporated into the feedback control loop as an additional input to improve pitch control response. Simultaneously, the pitch angle,

combined with the TSR, is used as input for the feed-forward torque control. These variables are employed to compute the power coefficient (C_p), which enables the calculation of the feedforward aerodynamic torque. The feedforward torque control scheme is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Feedforward torque control block diagram.

The aerodynamic torque is calculated using equation Equation 3.

$$M_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^3 \frac{C_p(\lambda, \theta_{ff})}{\lambda} V_{0L}^2 \quad (3)$$

The feedforward torque controller uses the aerodynamic torque signal as input, comparing it against the rated torque provided by the feedback controller. The difference between these signals is used to adjust the generator torque, ensuring it remains aligned with the rated torque. This approach guarantees that the generator operates at its optimal torque, compensating for wind fluctuations and improving the overall performance of the system.

3.2 Neural Network pitch angle prediction

A fully connected Deep ONet neural network was implemented to predict the required θ_{ff} for mitigating tower motion. The training data used for the neural network consists of steady-state operation data from the 15 MW NREL wind turbine. To enhance the dataset, the steady-state thrust coefficient data was interpolated using cubic splines, generating additional training data. The interpolated data was plotted alongside the original wind turbine model data, showing the accuracy of the interpolation as depict in Figure 6. The dataset was then randomly split into training, validation, and test sets. Given the inherent complexity and non-linearity of the data, three additional input features were engineered in addition to C_t and λ by creating nonlinear combinations of these parameters: $C_t\lambda$, $C_t^2\lambda$, and $C_t\lambda^2$.

The neural network architecture consists of a fully connected model with 4 hidden layers, each containing 64 neurons, as shown in Figure 7. The model takes 5 input features (λ , C_t , $C_t\lambda$, $C_t^2\lambda$, $C_t\lambda^2$) and outputs the predicted pitch angle θ_{ff} . Input data is normalized to the $[0, 1]$ range, as the \tanh activation function is employed.

Figure 6: Cubi Spline interpolation of C_t coefficient.

This normalization step is embedded within the network's preprocessing pipeline.

Figure 7: Neural network architecture.

Training was optimized using the Adam optimization algorithm with an adaptive learning rate schedule, starting at 10^{-2} and decaying progressively to 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} at intervals of 5000 epochs. The training process was structured into 4 mini-batches per epoch, facilitating efficient convergence and mitigating the risk of overfitting through mini-batch gradient updates.

4 Results

In this section, the presented feedforward controller is evaluated, by analysing it and comparing it to the feedback controller as well as to the original feedforward pitch controller. Simulations are executed using the OpenFast aeroelastic model, with the turbine subjected to coherent gust.

First, the performance of the neural network is evaluated by calculating the Mean Squared Error (MSE) over a dataset of 2000 points, resulting in an MSE of 0.00006 for the normalized data—a low value considering the size of the dataset. Figure 8 shows a histogram of the prediction error in degrees, revealing deviations of 1 to 2 degrees in some operational conditions. This indicates that the non-linearity of the data poses challenges for accurate approximation, suggesting potential room for further improvement.

Figure 8: Error histogram for Neural Network Prediction.

Secondly, a brute force optimization was performed to fine-tune the proportional gain of the pitch feedforward rate and the time buffer, t_{buffer} , for the feedforward control to minimize the cost function. After running multiple simulations, the optimal values were determined to be $T_{buffer} = 2.8$ seconds and $K = 1.1$, resulting in a cost value of $cost = 0.1926$, which is considered optimal for this task. The cost function map from the optimization process is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Cost function optimization map.

As shown in Figure 10, the multivariable feedforward

controller demonstrates superior performance relative to the other controllers. Table 1 presents deviations from rated conditions, where the proposed controller achieves a 67,87% reduction in rotor speed deviation compared to the feedback controller, matching the 67,94% reduction of the baseline feedforward controller. Additionally, the tower base Fore-Aft moment deviation is reduced by 90% relative to the feedback controller, significantly outperforming the baseline feedforward controller, which achieves a 51% reduction.

Deviation from rated conditions

	FB	FB+FF BL	FB+FF
$\Delta\Omega$ [rpm]	0.679	0.218	0.218
ΔM_{yt} [MNm]	247.8	121.4	25.91
ΔF_a [kN]	780.2	435.9	168.0
Cost	1.6553	0.7959	0.1926

Table 1

Figure 10: Wind turbine variables for the presented feedforward controller (red), compared to the feedback controller (blue) and the baseline task feedforward controller (yellow).

The proposed multivariable feedforward controller significantly reduces thrust, as shown in Figure 11, achieving a reduction of up to 22,4% compared to the feedback controller. This performance also surpasses the baseline feedforward controller, which provides a 12,6% reduction. The maximum values for the Rotor Thrust and the tower ForeAft moment are illustrated in Table 2.

Figure 11: Rotor Thrust for the presented feedforward controller (red), compared to the feedback controller (blue) and the baseline feedforward controller (yellow).

Maximum values

	FB	FB+FF BL	FB+FF
$F_{a_{max}}$ [kN]	2736	2392	2124
$M_{yt_{max}}$ [MNm]	350.2	229.8	172.6

Table 2: Comparing simulation results.

5 Conclusions and future work

This work presents a solution for the IEA Wind Task 53 LAC Summer Games, particularly for the “30s Sprint” discipline. The selected approach consists on the design of a multivariable feedforward controller for above rated conditions. The controller aims at keeping constant rotor motion and generator torque, where desired control actions for pitch and torque are calculated using an inverse wind turbine model.

A neural network predicts the required pitch angle based on the tip-speed ratio (TSR) and thrust coefficient, seeking constant thrust and smooth transitions during wind disturbances. Moreover, a feedforward torque signal is integrated in the torque controller, to account for changes in aerodynamic torque, and keep the generator torque constant. The integration of this feedforward controller with traditional feedback systems allows for more responsive control actions.

The results show significant improvements over baseline feedforward controllers, with reductions in rotor speed deviation (67.87% over the FB controller) and tower base fore-aft bending moments (90%). Additionally, a 22.4% reduction in rotor thrust is achieved. These findings suggest that the multivariable feedforward controller accompanied by a neural network, enhances wind turbine performance, particularly in managing the impact of extreme wind gusts.

A Deep ONet neural network was implemented to

demonstrate its capability for data prediction using operational data. This initial approach shows promising results with the available data. Leveraging known wind turbine operational data can enable the prediction of certain conditions and parameters, allowing for faster response times and improved control of operational conditions. This is only a simulation test case where the steady state data is known but this can be expanded to real operation conditions.

Future work will focus on modifying the input thrust value of the pitch feedforward controller by calculating the derivative of the thrust and minimizing it. This is thought to reduce even further the thrust variation, when subjected to wind disturbances. Additionally, the neural network can be expanded to work on a bigger set of conditions.

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